

Conductometric Study on the Quantitative Estimation of Thorium as Tungstate

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Conductometric titrations of thorium nitrate against sodium tungstate have been carried out at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ and the effect of the addition of ethanol on the results has been studied. The results obtained show that thorium is quantitatively precipitated as normal tungstate. Reverse titrations, however, have not provided any satisfactory results.

Britton and Meek¹ titrated potentiometrically as well as conductometrically acetate solutions of copper, lead, arsenic, beryllium, aluminium, and thorium with alkali hydroxides and Yoshinaga Oka², nitrate solutions of a number of metals including thorium with hydroxide, carbonate, phosphate, arsenate, vanadate, selenate, molybdate, and tungstate of sodium and with tellurate, chromate, ferri- and ferro-cyanides of potassium. Atanasiu³ carried out electrometric titrations of the salts of lanthanum, cerium, and thorium with solutions of sodium and ammonium oxalates. Menon and Singh⁴, while carrying out conductometric titrations of thorium chloride with oxalic acid, ammonium oxalate, and silver nitrate, found only oxalic acid as a satisfactory precipitant. Singh and Agarwala⁵ titrated thorium conductometrically with sebacic acid. Kabadi and co-workers⁶⁻⁷ studied electrometrically the formation of colloidal thorium molybdate at *pH* 4.13 and the interaction of thorium nitrate and mono- and di-potassium arsenates. Moeller and Dawson⁸ confirmed the formation of $\text{ThP}_2\text{O}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by conductometric and *pH*-metric titrations of thorium nitrate with $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_6$ solution. Gaur and Bhattacharya⁹ studied the formation of $\text{Th}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ by conductometric and potentiometric titrations. Deshmukh *et al.*¹⁰ titrated conductometrically thorium at *pH* 1.5-2.0 with selenous acid and found this method to be accurate, especially at lower concentrations. Thorium has been estimated conductometrically as normal metavanadate¹¹ and tellurite¹² in this laboratory.

The present communication records an account of the results of a series of conductometric titrations of thorium nitrate solution with sodium tungstate under varied experimental conditions.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium tungstate (Merck's A.R. quality) and thorium nitrate (May & Baker, Reagent quality) were dissolved separately in conductivity water. Thorium was estimated as ThO_2 after precipitation with oxalic acid. Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilutions.

Titration curves were carried out at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ in a Jena beaker (100 ml) with a dip cell of the type PR 9510 having the cell constant 1.44, Philips conductivity bridge of type PT9500; a 220-volt a.c. line-operated direct-reading electronic instrument with a magic eye as an indicator was used for the electrolytic resistance measurements. The readings were recorded in ohms at an output frequency of 50 cycles/second.

Effect of Ethanolic Concentration.—It was observed that titrations performed in purely aqueous medium did not provide correct values and neither the curves were smooth nor the breaks sharp and the end points were not well defined. Several titrations were therefore carried out at various ethanol concentrations ranging from 10-40%, all of which provided results very close to the theoretical value and improved the smoothness of the curves. The results are plotted in Fig. 1, curves I-V.

FIG. 1

Direct Conductometric Titrations.—A known volume of thorium nitrate solution was taken in a Jena beaker and made to 60 ml containing an overall 10% EtOH by volume. It was placed on the magnetic stirrer, the dip cell properly dipped, and the initial resistance recorded. Sodium tungstate was added from a microburette in small amounts. After each addition, the mixture was stirred well, allowed to settle, and the resistance recorded. The reciprocals of the resistances were plotted against the volume of the titrant (Fig. 1, curves I—VI).

Reverse Conductometric Titrations.—In this set a known volume of sodium tungstate solution was taken, made to 60 ml containing 10% of ethanol by volume, and thorium nitrate solution added from a microburette. Other procedures were the same as for the direct titrations. The results are plotted in Fig. 1, curves I-III.

TABLE I

 Molarity of the diluted sodium tungstate soln. = 0.2032*M*.

S. No.	%EtOH.	Th(NO ₃) ₄ soln.	Na ₂ WO ₄ soln.	Molar ratio of Th:W.
A. Direct titration.				
1	0	4.00 ml	0.55 ml	1:2.616
2	10	4.00	0.42	1:1.997
3	20	4.00	0.41	1:1.950
4	30	4.00	0.42	1:1.997
5	40	4.00	0.41	1:1.950
6	10	3.06	0.31	1:1.966
7	10	3.50	0.36	1:1.955
8	10	4.00	0.42	1:1.997
9	10	4.50	0.47	1:1.986
10	10	5.00	0.52	1:1.978
11	10	5.50	0.57	1:1.972
12	10	6.00	0.63	1:1.997
*B. Reverse titration.				
1		0.13 ml	0.004786 <i>M</i>	1:4.390
2		0.22	0.001355	1:3.459
3		0.43	0.001693	1:2.785

N.B.—In reverse titrations molarity of thorium soln. was 0.1068*M* and volume of tungstate soln., 60 ml.

DISCUSSION

The reactions involved in the present titrations of thorium nitrate with sodium tungstate may be represented as:

The unsuitability of aqueous medium for the quantitative and complete precipitation of thorium is probably due to the slight dissociation of the precipitate or its hydrolysis, which is remedied by addition of ethanol

In direct titrations, breaks obtained correspond to the molar ratio 1:2 of thorium and tungsten and it thus lends support to the formation of normal thorium tungstate. In reverse titrations, premature end-points were obtained and the ratio of Th:W was less than two in all the cases. This may be due to either the adsorption of WO_4^{2-} on precipitated $\text{Th}(\text{WO}_4)_2$ or the formation of isopoly acid between $\text{Th}(\text{WO}_4)_2$ and Na_2WO_4 .

The authors' grateful thanks are due to authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities and to the Ministry of Education, Govt. of India, for awarding a research training scholarship to one of them (S.D.K.).

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Received June 4, 1965.